

EFFECTIVE USE OF LEARNING GAMES FOR SUCCESSFUL ENGLISH LANGUAGE ACQUISITION BY SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS

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Түйін: Мақалада ағылшын тілі сабағында оқылымды дамытуға арналған ойын түрлерін қолдану және сол ойындардың оқушылардың оқудағы үлгеріміне тиімді әсер етуі туралы айтылады.

Резюме: В статье обсуждается использование игр для развития чтения на уроках английского языка и их положительных влияниях на успеваемость учащихся.

The game is a specially organized activity that requires emotional and mental strength. This is an equal game, accessible even to the weakest students. Even the weakest student in language training can become a leader in the game: resourcefulness and ingenuity are sometimes more important than knowledge of the subject. A sense of equality, interest, a favorable atmosphere created during the game, the fulfillment of tasks and assigned tasks - all this makes it possible for children to overcome shyness and has a beneficial effect on the process and the result of training. Imperceptibly assimilated language material, and with it, children have a feeling of satisfaction that they can speak on a par with everyone in the group. Also, games in a foreign language class can and should be used to relieve tension, monotony, while working out language material, while enhancing speech activity. The use of games in foreign language lessons helps the teacher to more deeply reveal the personal potential of each student, his positive personal qualities (diligence, activity, independence, flexibility, initiative, ability to work in a team, etc.).

The game, as you know, is the main activity of the child. It is a kind of common language for all children. At the same time, the game is a teaching toolkit that activates the students' mental activity, makes the

learning process attractive and interesting, and has an emotional impact on students. This is a powerful incentive to master the language. According to psychologists (A. A. Leontiev and others), the motivation created by the game should be presented along with communicative, cognitive and aesthetic motivation. All this taken together constitutes the motivation of the teaching. The most powerful motivating factor is the teaching methods that satisfy the need of schoolchildren in the novelty of the material being studied, in the variety of exercises performed. The use of a variety of teaching methods helps to consolidate linguistic phenomena in the memory, creating more persistent visual and auditory images, and maintaining student interest and activity. Nowadays, the idea of the need to teach foreign languages as communication without fail in collective activities with regard to personal and interpersonal relations has also become obvious: teacher - group, teacher - student, student - group, student - student.

In addition to all of the above, the game is a particularly organized exercise that requires emotional and mental stress. The game always involves making a decision: what to do, what to say, how to win? The desire to solve these issues sharpens the mental activity of the players. And if the child will speak in a foreign language? Are there rich learning opportunities here? Undoubtedly, the game is feasible even for weak students. Moreover, a student who is weak in language training can become the first in the game: resourcefulness and ingenuity are sometimes more important here than knowledge of the subject. The feeling of equality, the atmosphere of enthusiasm and joy, the feeling of the feasibility of the task - all this allows students to speak freely in a foreign language.

We know that playing is fun, fun and funny. It can be said that the game is one of the easiest ways to achieve educational and educational goals. Games help not only to fix the material covered, but also to repeat it over time. The game helps to make students work actively in the classroom. In a game, a weak student becomes confident and takes an active part in it. In the lesson, the students' attention is often scattered, and again a game comes to the rescue, which concentrates the attention of the students, increases their interest in the subject being studied. In the game, you can easily and quickly correct the mistakes of students. Children remember the material easily and for a long time during the game. You can use the game at the beginning of a lesson to interest children, get their attention or repeat the material covered. The game can be applied in the middle of a lesson or at the end of a lesson, i.e. games can be used in class

at any time. Many famous teachers paid attention to the effectiveness of the use of games in the learning process. E.I. Passov, Ph.D., in the book "Foreign Language Lesson at School" gives the following definition of a game: "... A game is: 1) activity 2) motivation, lack of coercion 3) individualized activity, deeply personal 4) training and education in a team through the team 5) development of mental functions and abilities, 6) "learning with passion" (in the words of S. L. Soloveichik) "The game is a powerful incentive to master a foreign language and an effective reception in the arsenal of a foreign language teacher, able to turn a foreign language teacher into a rather complicated learning process into an engaging and favorite lesson. "

The game is a specially organized lesson that requires emotional tension and mental strength from the child. While playing, the child solves the following questions: what to do and what to do in this or that situation? In the process of solving these issues, the mental activity of students develops. The game form of classes is created in the classroom with the help of game techniques and situations that act as a means of motivation, incentives for learning activities. The teacher often uses the game method of learning in foreign language lessons. Of course, it is impossible to work only with the use of the game method, because learning will lose its basic meaning. In our lessons we combine the game method with other teaching methods. Teaching younger students a foreign language is preparatory in nature for the subsequent stage of training and is based on practical, educational and educational purposes. To achieve these goals it is necessary to use different techniques, methods aimed at enhancing the activity of the child. It is necessary to select such tasks that create a certain language environment and are very popular with children. The productivity of using game situations in foreign language lessons is very obvious. In the process of playing activity, along with mental development, aesthetic and moral education is carried out. Working on the FORWARD TMC in the second grade and observing the results of teaching children English, we encountered difficulties in memorizing the English vocabulary for children; therefore, they began to use lexical games more often in the classroom.

Lexical games help to form a lexical minimum among students, which is necessary for communication. They acquaint children with the compatibility of words, develop speech. In the process of lexical games vocabulary of the student is replenished. In English classes, children like to play the following games:

1. What's missing? We post from 6 to 10 cards in front of children. We ask them to close their eyes. We remove one picture. Please open your eyes and say that it's gone.

2. What's in the house? Cut out the cardboard figure of the house with a window. We show the picture through the window (only part of the picture should be visible). Children guess what is in the house. What's this? It's a car

3. Unscramble the words Kids love this game. You can start with simple words consisting of only three letters, for example: ath (hat) Gradually move to a more complex version: etalb (table) Such tasks help memorize the correct spelling of words, develop the memory of the child.

4. Memory game. The teacher gives students the task to remember words on any topic. The student calls the word relating to the given topic, the second student repeats it and adds his own, the third calls the first two words and adds his word.

5. Were you ...? The pupil depicts an animal, such as a cat. He performs various actions characteristic of this animal (for example, jumping). Pupils try to guess which animal he portrayed: - Were you a dog? - No, I was not a dog. Questions are asked until then. While one of the children does not guess the intended animal. The guesser becomes the leader.

6. Be quick. The student starts the game by saying a word in English. Representatives of the teams take turns calling the word that begins with the last letter of the previous word, for example: red, dress, small etc. If the player is unable to quickly come up with the word, he is eliminated from the game. The winner is the team in which by the end of the game there are more students left.

7. Have you got ..? The student hides a toy behind his back. The rest of the students guess what is behind him, asking questions: Have you got a cat? Leading answers: Yes, I have or No, I have not.

8. "Imitators" The teacher calls any animal, bird or profession, and the children try to mimic, voice and gestures to depict the name. The winner is the one who succeeds. It is necessary to instill in children an interest in the learning process and in a foreign language.

The child is able to memorize language material in whole blocks. This is easiest in the game. It is safe to say that the child's abilities are manifested in the game. It is revealed from the most unexpected sides, it is interesting and understandable to him. We use the same game at different stages of the lesson. The use of the game teaching method develops the speech skills of children, helps to show independence in solving verbal-thinking

tasks, develops a quick reaction in communication. The teacher uses the game to solve various educational tasks, and for children the game is an exciting and entertaining lesson. In the game, all children are equal, this allows students to overcome the feeling of fear of making a mistake. The game requires concentration, trains memory, develops speech. Game exercises carry away even the weakest students. In conclusion, I would like to say that games develop memory, imagination, attention. Games help children become creative individuals. The use of games in a foreign language class helps the teacher to uncover the student's personal potential and contribute to the development of positive personal qualities of students. Playing in a foreign language class brings the process of communication in this language closer to natural communication. Planning a lesson, we try to create opportunities for the individual development of each child.

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